

Drug combination study of novel oxorhenium(V) complexes

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Abstract

Three new Re(V) complexes of structural formulas $[\text{ReOCl}_2\text{L}(\text{PPh}_3)]$, where L is pyridine-2-carboxylic acid (**C1**), 3-methyl-pyridine-2-carboxylic acid (**C2**) and 6-methyl-pyridine-2-carboxylic acid (**C3**) were synthesized and characterized using NMR, IR spectroscopy and mass spectrometry. Crystal structure of all three complexes has been additionally confirmed by X-ray analysis. The biological activity has been investigated in the panel of tumor cell lines A549, PANC-1, MDA-MB-231, MCF-7, LS-174, EAhy.926 and one non-tumor cell

line MRC-5. Only **C1** showed dose-dependent cytotoxic potential, particularly toward triple-negative breast adenocarcinoma cells MDA-MB-231 with IC_{50} $68.90 \pm 1.73 \mu\text{M}$ and pancreatic adenocarcinoma cells PANC-1 with IC_{50} $69.84 \pm 2.3 \mu\text{M}$. Both cell lines are characterized by highly invasive and resistant phenotype. Drug combination studies in PANC-1 cells with **C1** and Verapamil hydrochloride (VRP) which is the established inhibitor of efflux transporter P-glycoprotein (Pgp), revealed enhancement of antiproliferative action of complex in dose-dependent manner, and slight arrest of cell cycle in the S phase. Also, depletion of GSH level by L-buthionine-sulfoximine (L-BSO) at sub-toxic concentrations ($100 \mu\text{M}$) caused enhancement of activity of **C1** to the IC_{50} $57.67 \pm 6.51 (\mu\text{M})$. Morphological analysis in PANC-1 cells by dual acridine orange/ethidium bromide staining, revealed apoptotic potential of complex **C1** and slower kinetic of cell death induction, suggesting different mechanism of action comparing to cisplatin.

Keywords: rhenium(V) complex, crystal structure, cytotoxic activity, breast carcinoma cells, pancreatic carcinoma cells, GSH pathway

1. Introduction

In spite of continuous research efforts, cancer remains as one of the leading causes of death in the world [1]. Cancer is generally not a single disease and can evolve in almost any type of cell in the human body and spread to other tissues and organs, either by direct invasion of neighboring tissue or move to distant parts of the body by metastasis [2]. Therefore, each type of cancer requires an individual therapeutic approach. In 2018, cancer caused an estimated 9.6 million deaths worldwide, with about 1.9 million cases alone in the European Union [3]. In addition to surgery and radiotherapy, anticancer chemotherapy based on

cytotoxic drugs is an important pillar of essentially every therapeutic approach on malignant diseases. Since the discovery of metal-based drugs such as cisplatin, oxaliplatin, and carboplatin in the late 1960s, the field of metallochemotherapeutics has steadily expanded to mainly ruthenium and osmium complex emerging as the most promising candidates [4]. Among many metal-based compounds, rhenium complexes merit particular attention, due to its wide range of oxidation states (-1 to +7), giving the opportunity to synthesize complexes with great structural diversity and ability to modulate the redox status of cancer cells in addition to their general low toxicity [5]. Radioactive rhenium isotopes, ^{186}Re and ^{188}Re , were evaluated as potential radiopharmaceuticals since they have β -emission suitable for anticancer activity or γ -emission for imaging. Non-radioactive luminescence rhenium carbonyl compounds have been studied as imaging and phototoxic agents [6]. However, the potential of cytotoxic rhenium complexes has not been evaluated so far to significant degree and has been mainly focused on Re(I) carbonyl compounds [7]. Synthesis and characterization of first rhenium(I) tricarbonyl complexes has been reported in the beginning of 1940's [8] but the first rhenium organometallic complexes that expressed significant antitumor activity were alkoxo/hydroxo carbonyl complexes, $[\text{Re}_2(\mu\text{-OH})_3(\text{CO})_6]$, $[\text{Re}_2(\mu\text{-OH})(\mu\text{-OPh})_2(\text{CO})_6]$, $[\text{Re}_2(\mu\text{-OMe})_2(\mu\text{-dppf})_2(\text{CO})_6]$ and $[\text{Re}_2(\mu\text{-OPh})_2(\mu\text{-dppf})_2(\text{CO})_6]$ (dppf = 1,10-bis(diphenylphosphino)-ferrocene), synthesized and evaluated in 2000's [9]. Further evaluation of rhenium(I) tricarbonyl complexes showed that biological activity of these complexes is based on the kinetically inert $[\text{Re}^I(\text{CO})_3]^+$ core. Also, depending on the ligand nature (cyclopentadienyl, iminedipyridyl, N,N-bis(quinolone), phenantroline, diphenylphenantroline), these complexes could show phosphorescence/luminescence properties and serve as potential photosensitizers and bioimaging agents [10,6a,9a]. Generally, Re(I) tricarbonyl compounds with chelating ligands based on N^N, N^O, and O^O chelators most probably induce cytotoxic effects by covalent interaction with the nucleobases

of DNA and/or protein functional groups, but the mechanism of action, however is not often fully elucidated [11,7]. Specific group of rhenium(I) tricarbonyl complexes with pyridine, bipyridine and phenantroline based ligands has been synthesized as potential mitochondria-target antitumor agents. The cytotoxicity of these complexes was superior to cisplatin against all human cancer cell lines with IC₅₀ values in low micromolar ranges, including cisplatin-resistant cells [12,13,6a]. Despite significant *in vitro* evaluation results for number of rhenium(I) tricarbonyl complexes, only few were investigated *in vivo* probably due to toxicity against normal cells. [Re(CO)₃(dmphen)H₂O] (dmphen = 2,9-dimethyl-1,10-phenanthroline) and rhenium(I) diselenoether complexes were the most promising candidates for further *in vivo* evaluations [14]. Beside rhenium(I) complexes, which were investigated in depth, rhenium(V) complexes took a primate in latest cytotoxic research. Different ligand systems (N^S, N^O, N^N) and parent rhenium(V) compounds were used but only few of them stood up expressing promising antitumor activity. However, oxorhenium(V) were the most evaluated and biologically active complexes. Oxorhenium(V) based compounds with chelate N^S thiosemicarbazone ligands expressed very good antitumor activity with nanomolar IC₅₀ values only in the presence of at least one very labile leaving chloride ligand [15]. Beside mentioned complexes, most of other N^S oxorhenium(V) were evaluated as target compounds for different receptors responsible for tumor cell growth. The most promising antitumor activity results to date expressed two new oxorhenium(V) phenantroline complexes (Fig. 1). The potency of these rhenium(V) complexes was significantly higher than cisplatin's for all the cell lines tested and at the same time exhibited selectivity toward cancer cells over normal cells. These compounds induce specific necrotic cell death including generation of intracellular ROS and depolarization of cell membrane. *In vivo* tests revealed stability of these complexes in blood comparable to cisplatin, as well as similar cytotoxicity [16]. Having in mind very good *in vitro* antitumor activity results for rhenium(I) tricarbonyl

phenantroline complexes it could be concluded that this type of ligand stabilizes rhenium in both oxidation states, +1 and +5, and contributes to antitumor activity of these complexes.

Fig. 1. Chemical structures of representative antitumor active oxorhenium(V) complexes

Some of rhenium based compounds such as Re-bisphosphonates, Re-labeled liposomes, Re-peptide, Re-sulfure materials entered clinical trials. Three of them were radio labeled peptide and liposomes oxorhenium(V) complexes, with radioisotopes ^{188}Re and ^{186}Re . The most promising one was P2045, oxorhenium(V) labeled peptide, which is still in Phase II of clinical trials for different lung cancers [6a,17,18].

Picolinic acid (pyridine-2-carboxylic acid) and its derivatives tightly coordinate to metal ions as a bidentate N[^]O-donor forming a stable five-membered chelate ring demonstrating the dual functionality of the two donor sites. The carboxylate oxygen atom, as a hard donor stabilizes transition metals in higher oxidation states, while the pyridine nitrogen, softer donor prefers coordination to metal in its lower oxidation states [19]. Metal based complexes with this type of chelating ligands possess diverse biological applications, from dietary supplementation to carcinostatics, antitumor, antiviral and antibacterial activity [20,21,22]. Osmium(II) and iridium(III) picolinate based complexes have been attracting attention in the last years due to showed activity towards various human cancer cell line with IC_{50} values in μM range [23,24]. Rhenium(V) complexes with picolinic based ligands were used mostly in

different catalytic processes [25]. In the light of the significant antitumor activity of some oxorhenium(V) complexes, we investigated oxorhenium(V) picolinate as potentially antitumor active compounds.

Pancreatic adenocarcinoma is very aggressive disease that develops in a relatively symptom-free manner and is characterized by high resistance to standard anticancer drugs [26,27]. Resistance is most often mediated by ATP dependent-drug efflux pumps such as transmembrane glycoprotein (P-glycoprotein-Pgp) or Multidrug Resistance Associated Proteins (MRPs), which are responsible for efflux of many structurally unrelated drugs including the organic anions conjugated to glutathione [28].

Herein we describe synthesis, chemical characterization and antitumor activity of three new Re(V) complexes. The mechanism of biological action of the most active rhenium complex was analyzed in pancreatic adenocarcinoma cells (PANC-1). Finally, the effect of pharmacological inhibition of Pgp transporter and glutathione (GSH) biosynthesis to action of tested Re(V) complexes was investigated.

2. Experimental Section

2.1. Materials and Methods

$[\text{ReOCl}_3(\text{PPh}_3)_2]$ was prepared according to a published procedure [29]. Pyridine-2-carboxylic acid (picolinic acid) (**HL1**), 3-methylpyridine-2-carboxylic acid (**HL2**) and 6-methylpyridine-2-carboxylic acid (**HL3**) were purchased from Acros organics. **C1** already described in the literature, herein has been synthesized using modified procedure [25]. As a solvent acetonitrile was used instead of methanol and reaction time was prolonged for two hours. Single crystals were obtained by slow evaporation of mother liquor solution. Solvents

were obtained and used without further purification. Infrared spectra were recorded on Nicolet 6700 FTIR spectrometer, using the ATR technique (Fig. S1-S3). ^1H and ^{13}C spectra were acquired on a Varian instrument (Agilent, USA) with a 5 mm ATB probe, using standard pulse sequences, at 399.73 MHz for ^1H and 100.52 MHz for ^{13}C nuclei. Chemical shifts for ^1H and ^{13}C were referenced to residual ^1H and ^{13}C present in CDCl_3 (Figs. S4-S9). ESI mass spectra were measured on mass spectrometer LTQ Orbitrap XL using CH_3CN (Fig. S10-S12). Elemental analyses were performed at the Microanalytical Service of the Faculty of Chemistry, University of Vienna. X-ray analyses were performed at the Institute of Chemistry, University of Graz, Austria, using monochromatized Mo K_α radiation at 100K [30]. **C1:** $\text{C}_{24}\text{H}_{19}\text{Cl}_2\text{NO}_3\text{PRe}$, M_r 657.47, monoclinic, space group C c, $a = 7.5444(6)\text{\AA}$, $b = 39.252(3)\text{\AA}$, $c = 7.8754(6)\text{\AA}$, $\beta = 96.220(5)^\circ$, $V = 2318.5(3)\text{\AA}^3$, $Z = 4$, $d_{\text{calc}} = 1.884\text{ g cm}^{-3}$; $R1 = 0.0337$ (293 parameters, 4531 unique reflections). **C2:** $\text{C}_{25}\text{H}_{21}\text{Cl}_2\text{NO}_3\text{PRe}$, M_r 671.50, monoclinic, space group P $2_1/c$, $a = 7.5811(6)\text{\AA}$, $b = 39.165(4)\text{\AA}$, $c = 7.8657(7)\text{\AA}$, $\beta = 96.531(5)^\circ$, $V = 2320.3(4)\text{\AA}^3$, $Z = 4$, $d_{\text{calc}} = 1.922\text{ g cm}^{-3}$; $R1 = 0.0580$ (305 parameters, 5542 unique reflections). **C3:** $\text{C}_{25}\text{H}_{21}\text{Cl}_2\text{NO}_3\text{PRe}$, M_r 671.50, monoclinic, space group P $2_1/c$, $a = 7.8790(3)\text{\AA}$, $b = 37.8688(16)\text{\AA}$, $c = 7.8750(4)\text{\AA}$, $\beta = 95.958(2)^\circ$, $V = 2336.96(18)\text{\AA}^3$, $Z = 4$, $d_{\text{calc}} = 1.909\text{ g cm}^{-3}$; $R1 = 0.0482$ (304 parameters, 6205 unique reflections). Further crystallographic data, refinement description, figures and selected geometry parameters are given in the Supporting Information (Figs. S13-S14, Tables S1-S2). CCDC 2126604-2126606 contain the supplementary crystallographic data for this paper. These data can be obtained free of charge via www.ccdc.cam.ac.uk/data_request/cif.

2.2. Synthesis of Complexes

2.2.1. Synthesis of dichloro-oxo-triphenylphosphine-(pyridine-2-carboxylato-N,O)-rhenium(V) [ReOCl₂(L1)(PPh₃)] (**C1**)

A suspension of **HL1** (0.03 g, 0.24 mmol) in acetonitrile (5 mL) was added to suspension of [ReOCl₃(PPh₃)₂] (0.20 g, 0.24 mmol) in acetonitrile (5 mL). The reaction mixture was refluxed for 3h at 78 °C resulting in a brown clear solution. Purple crystals were grown in one week from reaction solution following the slow solvent evaporation. Yield 49.14 %. IR (ATR) $\nu_{\max}/\text{cm}^{-1}$: 502.4 (**Re–O** st), 530.2 (**Re–N** st), 712.7–690.4 (ar **C–H** δ) 992.1 (**Re=O** st), 1096.7 (**P–C** st), 1614.0 (**C=N** st), 1689.79 (**C=O** st), 3057.5 (ar **C–H** st). ¹H NMR (399.73 MHz, CDCl₃) δ (ppm) = 7.33–7.66 (m, 16H, **PPh₃** and **H⁵**); 8.39–8.49 (m, 2H, **H³** and **H⁴**); 12.02 (d, 1H, **H⁶**). ¹³C NMR (100.52 MHz, CDCl₃) δ (ppm) = 125.49–148.14 (PyC + **PPh₃**); 164.74 (**C=O**). Anal. Calculated for RePC₂₄H₁₉NO₃Cl₂ (%): N 2.13; C 43.84; H 2.89; found (%): N 21.91; C 44.04; H 2.99. ESI/MS (m/z), CH₃CN: positive mode 657.00 [M]⁺; 622.03 [M–Cl]⁺ (calculated [M]⁺ for RePC₂₄H₁₉NO₃Cl₂ is 657)

2.2.2. Synthesis of dichloro-(3-methylpyridine-2-carboxylato-N,O)-oxo-triphenylphosphine-rhenium(V) [ReOCl₂(L2)(PPh₃)] (**C2**)

The **C2** was synthesized using the same procedure as for **C1** using [ReOCl₃(PPh₃)₂] (0.20 g, 0.24 mmol) and **HL2** (0.03 g, 0.24 mmol). Red crystals were grown in one week from reaction solution following the slow solvent evaporation. Yield 39.11 %. IR (ATR) $\nu_{\max}/\text{cm}^{-1}$: 502.1 (**Re–O** st), 530.6 (**Re–N** st), 711.8–691.8 (ar **C–H** δ) 988.2 (**Re=O** st), 1098.7 (**P–C** st), 1612.6 (**C=N** st), 1700.5 (**C=O** st), 3058.5 (ar **C–H** st). ¹H NMR (399.73

MHz, CDCl₃) δ (ppm) = 2.23 (s, 3H, CH₃); 7.29–7.53 (m, 17H, PPh₃, H⁴ and H⁵); 8.42 (d, 1H, H⁶). ¹³C NMR (100.52 MHz, CDCl₃) δ (ppm) = 19.41 (CH₃); 126.39–153.20 (PyC + PPh₃); 165.19 (C=O). Anal. Calculated for RePC₂₅H₂₁NO₃Cl₂ (%): N 2.09; C 44.71; H 3.13; found (%): N 2.12; C 44.94; H 3.00. ESI/MS (m/z), CH₃OH: positive mode 694.20 [M+Na]⁺ (calculated for NaRePC₂₅H₂₁NO₃Cl₂ is 694.20) and 709.98 [M+K]⁺ (calculated for KRePC₂₅H₂₁NO₃Cl₂ is 710.20)

2.2.3. Synthesis of dichloro-(6-methylpyridine-2-carboxylato-N,O)-oxo-triphenylphosphine-rhenium(V) [ReOCl₂(L3)(PPh₃)] (**C3**)

The **C3** was synthesized using the same procedure as for **C1** using [ReOCl₃(PPh₃)₂] (0.20 g, 0.24 mmol) and **HL3** (0.03 g, 0.24 mmol). Blue crystals were grown in one week from reaction solution following the slow solvent evaporation. Yield 64.60 %. IR (ATR) ν_{\max} /cm⁻¹: 501.4 (Re–O st), 529.3 (Re–N st), 760.9–691.8 (ar C–H) 994.0 (Re=O st), 1095.4 (P–C st), 1614.4 (C=N st), 1707.0 (C=O st), 3057.7 (ar C–H st). ¹H NMR (399.73 MHz, CDCl₃) δ (ppm) = 2.93 (s, 3H, CH₃); 7.28–7.48 (m, 16H, PPh₃ and H⁴); 7.55 (d, 1H, H³); 7.62 (d, 1H, H⁵). ¹³C NMR (100.52 MHz, CDCl₃) δ (ppm) = 30.84 (CH₃); 126.39–153.20 (PyC + PPh₃); 165.19 (C=O). Anal. Calculated for RePC₂₅H₂₁NO₃Cl₂ (%): N 2.09; C 44.71; H 3.13; found (%): N 1.87; C 45.23; H 3.06. ESI/MS (m/z), CH₃OH: positive mode 636.05 [M–Cl]⁺ (calculated for RePC₂₅H₂₁NO₃Cl₂ is 671).

3. Biological Studies

3.1. Cell culture

The human lung adenocarcinoma cells (A549), human pancreatic adenocarcinoma cells (PANC-1), human colon adenocarcinoma cells (LS-174), endothelial cells (EA.hy 926) and human fetal lung fibroblast cells (MRC-5) were maintained as monolayer culture in the Roswell Park Memorial Institute (RPMI) 1640 nutrient medium (Sigma Chemicals Co, USA). The breast adenocarcinoma cell lines MDA-MB-231 and MCF-7 were cultured in Dulbecco's modified Eagle's medium (DMEM) (Sigma-Aldrich Co). All media were supplemented with 10% fetal calf serum (FCS) (pH 7.2) (Sigma-Aldrich Co), 2 mM L-glutamine, 25 mM 4-(2-hydroxyethyl) piperazine-1-ethanesulfonic acid (HEPES, Capricorn), and Penicillin-Streptomycin solution (Sigma-Aldrich Co) at a final concentration of 100 U/mL penicillin and 100 µg/mL streptomycin. The cells were grown at 37 °C in a humidified atmosphere containing 5% CO₂.

3.2. MTT assay

The antiproliferative activity of investigated rhenium complexes (**C1–C3**) and cisplatin (**CDDP**) was determined using the 3-(4,5-dimethylthiazol-yl)-2,5-diphenyltetrazolium bromide (MTT, Sigma) assay as previously described [30,31]. Briefly, 24 h after seeding the cells into 96-well cell culture plates (Thermo Scientific Nunc™), cells were exposed to the investigated complexes. The complexes were dissolved in dimethyl sulfoxide (DMSO) at a concentration of 10 mM and afterwards diluted in culture medium to obtain the final concentrations: 100; 50; 25; 12,5; 6,25 (µM). Each concentration was tested in triplicates,

while final DMSO concentration never exceeded 1% (v/v). After an incubation period of 72 h, 20 μ L of MTT solution (5 mg/mL in phosphate buffer, pH 7.2) was added to each well. Samples were incubated for 4 h at 37 °C in a humidified atmosphere of 5% CO₂, and then 100 μ L of 10% sodium dodecyl sulfate (SDS) was added. Absorbance was recorded after 24 h, on an enzyme linked immunosorbent assay (ELISA) reader (Thermo Labsystems Multiskan EX 200–240 V), at the wavelength of 570 nm. The IC₅₀ value, defined as the concentration of the compound causing 50% cell growth inhibition, was determined from the cell viability diagrams.

3.3. Drug combination study

Verapamil hydrochloride, 5-[N-(3,4-Dimethoxyphenylethyl)methylamino]-2-(3,4-dimethoxyphenyl)-2-isopropylvaleronitrile hydrochloride (VRP), as sterile saline solution 2,5mg/mL, ampule of 2 mL, was obtained from Alkaloid (Skoplje). The L-buthionine-sulfoximine (L-BSO) were purchased from Sigma-Aldrich as powder and dissolved in a physiological saline solution, at a final concentration of 10 mM, and sterilized by filtration (0.2 μ m pore-size filters). The stock solutions were wrapped in foil and kept at -20 °C.

3.3.1. Effects of VRP on C1–C3 – treated PANC-1 cells

Effect of VRP, the specific pharmacological blocker of P-glycoprotein (Pgp) [32], in combined action with C1–C3 or cisplatin, was measured by MTT (3-(4,5-dimethylthiazol-2-yl)-2,5-diphenyltetrazolium bromide) assay, as previously described [33]. Sensitivity of PANC-1 cells to VRP as a single agent, was tested in range of concentrations up to 1 mM and sub-toxic concentrations were chosen for combinational drug study. PANC-1 cell were pre-

treated with VRP for 30 min., and treatment continued for 72 h, in co-incubation with **C1–C3** or **CDDP**, applied in concentrations (μM): 6.25, 12.5, 25, 50, 100 μM . Cells incubated with VRP only, under the same treatment conditions were used as control. Each concentration was tested in triplicates.

3.3.2. Effects of L-BSO on C1 – treated PANC-1 cells

L-BSO, pharmacological inhibitor of glutathione synthesis, was applied in combination with **C1** or **CDDP** in PANC-1 cells, and cell survival measured following 72 h continual action, using MTT assay [33]. Briefly, PANC-1 cells were pre-treated with L-BSO at sub-toxic concentration 100 μM , for 1 h, and after **C1** or **CDDP** were added, in range of concentrations (μM): 6.25, 12.5, 25, 50, 100 μM , and treatment continued for 72 h. Cells incubated with L-BSO only, were used as control. Each concentration was tested in triplicates.

3.4. Cell cycle analysis

Analysis of the cell cycle phase distribution of PANC-1 cells after treatment with **C1** and **CDDP** in the presence or absence of VRP, was performed by flow cytometric analysis of the DNA content after staining with propidium iodide (PI) [34]. The cells were seeded at a density of 2×10^5 cells per well, into 6-well plates (Thermo Scientific Nunc™), in the nutrition medium. The cells were exposed to VRP (30 μM) or nutrient medium for 30 min. After **C1** or **CDDP** were added at concentrations 100 μM and 10 μM (respectively), and treatment carried out continuously for additional 48 h. Control cells were incubated in a nutrient medium or VRP (30 μM) only. After 48 h of growth, the cells were collected, washed twice with ice-cold phosphate-buffered saline (PBS), and fixed overnight, in 70%

ethanol. After fixation, the cells were washed with PBS, and incubated with Ribonuclease A (RNaseA, 1 mg/mL) for 30 min, at 37 °C. Immediately before flow-cytometric analysis, the cells were stained with PI, at a concentration of 400 µg/mL. Samples were analyzed using a fluorescence activated cell sorter (FACS), by Calibur Becton Dickinson flow cytometer, at 488 nm excitation line (Argon-ion laser). The data were analyzed by Cell Quest computer software.

3.5. Morphological analysis by fluorescent microscopy

The PANC-1 cells (1×10^5) were seeded on coverslips into 6-well plates (ThermoScientific Nunc™) in 2 mL of the nutrient medium. After 24 h of growth, the cells were treated with **C1** or **CDDP**. Following 72 h of treatment, the cells were stained with ethidium bromide (3 µg/mL) and acridine orange (5 µg/mL), according to standard procedures [35,36] and immediately after, observed under the fluorescent microscope – Carl Zeiss PALM MicroBeam with Axio Observer.Z1 using AxioCam MRm (filters Alexa Fluor 489 and Alexa Fluor 546) using the Zeiss Fluar 10×/0.50 or LD Plan-NeoFluar 20×/0.4 objectives. Images were obtained with multidimensional acquisition using digital imaging software (AxioVision Version 4.91; Carl Zeiss Imaging Solutions).

4. Results and discussion

4.1. Synthesis and characterization

Three new oxorhenium(V) complexes (**C1–C3**) were synthesized in the reaction of pyridine-2-carboxylic acid (**HL1**), 3-methylpyridine-2-carboxylic acid (**HL2**) and 6-methylpyridine-2-

carboxylic acid (**HL3**) with $[\text{ReOCl}_3(\text{PPh}_3)_2]$ (Scheme 1). All syntheses were performed in acetonitrile solution. Crystals of all three complexes were obtained from reaction solutions following the slow solvent evaporation. X-ray analysis and spectral measurement data confirmed that ligands **L1–L3** bound in a bidentate manner, *via* both oxygen and nitrogen atoms coordinated to the metal ion (Scheme 1).

Scheme 1. Reaction scheme describing the synthesis of the **C1–C3** complexes.

4.1.1. IR Spectroscopy

The IR spectra complexes confirmed bidentate type of ligand coordination *via* oxygen and nitrogen atoms. Lack of broad, intensive O-H stretching band vibration from $3453\text{--}2855\text{ cm}^{-1}$ indicated the involvement of carboxylate oxygen in coordination. In this region, sharp peak at 3057 cm^{-1} corresponding to aromatic **C-H** vibrations was observed in the spectra of all

complexes. Also, the broad absorption band in the range of 2649–2050 cm^{-1} in the spectra of all ligands indicates the presence of O-H...N type of intermolecular hydrogen bonding. This band was not noticed in the complexes which confirming the coordination of nitrogen atom to the rhenium ion. There is no significant change in wave number for symmetrical band of carbonyl group in spectra of complexes. The sharp strong band for P-C bond of triphenylphosphine ligand is located between 1095–1098 cm^{-1} (1096 cm^{-1} for **C1**; 1098 cm^{-1} for **C2**; 1095 cm^{-1} for **C3**). Finally, there is a slight change to the lower wave number in the Re=O bond due to coordination of additional ligand of metal ion.

4.1.2. NMR Spectroscopy

4.1.2.1. ^1H NMR Spectroscopy

In the ^1H NMR spectra of all synthesized complexes two similarities were noticed. First was the lack of the signal that corresponds to carboxylate proton, which confirmed ligands coordination via oxygen atoms. The second one was presence of a broad multiplet signals, corresponding to triphenylphosphine protons, in the range of 7.3–7.6 ppm. In the ^1H NMR spectrum of **C1** signal that corresponds to **H⁵** proton appears also in the range of 7.3–7.6 ppm. Multiplet signal in the range of 8.39–8.49 ppm corresponds to two protons **H³** and **H⁴** and is moved downfield comparing with the corresponding signal in the spectrum of free ligand. Doublet signal that corresponds to **H⁶** proton appears at 12.04 ppm which was the most significant change comparing with the signal of **L1** (8.78 ppm). This change is a consequence of **H⁶** proton vicinity to the nitrogen atom coordinated to the rhenium ion. In the ^1H NMR spectra of **C2** and **C3** singlet signals that correspond to methyl groups were found at 2.23 ppm and 2.93 ppm, respectively. Signals that correspond to **H⁴** and **H⁵** protons of **C2**

appeared in the range of 7.29–7.52 ppm and doublet signal at chemical shift of 8.42 ppm corresponds to **H**⁶. Signal from **H**⁴ proton appears in the range of 7.28–7.48 in the ¹H NMR spectrum of **C3** and two doublets at 7.55 ppm and 7.62 ppm correspond to **H**³ and **H**⁵ protons, respectively.

4.1.2.2. ¹³C NMR Spectroscopy

There were no significant changes in the ¹³C NMR spectra of synthesized complexes, comparing with the ligand spectra. Characteristic signals corresponding to the carbon atom from carbonyl group were around 164 ppm, signals for triphenylphosphine and carbon atoms from ligand moiety were in the area 125–148 ppm for **C1**, 126–153 ppm for **C2**, 123–147 ppm for **C3**). Signal for carbon atom from methyl group appeared at 19 ppm and 30 ppm in the ¹³C NMR spectrum of **C2** and **C3** respectively.

4.1.3. Mass spectrometry

The **C1**, **C2** and **C3** were also characterized by high resolution ESI-MS using positive ionization mode. In the mass spectra of **C1** two type of peaks, [M]⁺ ion and [M-Cl]⁺ ion were noticed. These high intense peaks were found at m/z values of 657.622 respectively. In the mass spectra of **C2**, [M+Na]⁺ (m/z = 694.20) and [M+K]⁺ (m/z = 709.98) were detected, while for **C3** one peak was detected corresponding to [M-Cl]⁺ ion at m/z value 636.

4.1.4. Crystal Structure

The crystal structure analyses confirmed the three substances **C1**, **C2** and **C3** as dichloro-oxo-triphenylphosphine-(pyridine-2-carboxylato-N,O)-rhenium(V) compounds (Figs. 2, S13, S14). All three compounds crystallize solvent-free and all atoms lie on general positions. Compound **C1** has the same modification at 100K as at room temperature [25]. Whereas the structure of compound **C1** is non-centrosymmetric, **C2** and **C3** show the same centrosymmetric packing. In all three compounds the bidentate ligand is bonded with the carboxylate group [Re1–O2 2.033(5)-2.043(6)Å, C2–O2 1.312(7)-1.339(10)Å] *trans* to the oxo atom [Re1–O1 1.669(5)-1.676(4)Å, O1–Re1–O2 158.4(3)-161.01(19)°], and the N atom of the pyridine ring [Re1–N11 2.127(9)-2.172(5)Å] *trans* to Cl1 [Re1–Cl1 2.327(2)-2.3387(15)Å, N11–Re1–Cl1 163.46(14)-170.5(2)°]. The octahedral coordination of the Re atom is completed by the triphenylphosphine ligand [Re1–P1 2.453(2)-2.4658(15)Å] *trans* to Cl2 [Re1–Cl2 2.371(3)-2.3837(15)Å, Cl2–Re1–P1 159.46(9)-164.85(5)°].

Fig. 2. Stereoscopic ORTEP plot of **C1** showing the atomic numbering scheme. The probability ellipsoids are drawn at the 50% probability level. The H atoms were omitted for clarity.

4.2. Biological assays

4.2.1. Results of MTT assay

The antiproliferative activity of the investigated rhenium complexes **C1–C3** and **CDDP** as a referent compound was determined in a panel of human cancer cell lines (A549, PANC-1, LS-174, EAhy.926, MDA-231 and MCF-7) and in one normal cell line (MRC-5) using MTT assay. Activity was determined after incubation of cells with investigated complexes for 72 h and results are presented in terms of IC_{50} values (μM) and cell survival diagrams (Table 1. and Fig. 3.). Only one examined complex **C1** showed dose-dependent cytotoxic potential, with IC_{50} values in the range of concentrations from 68.90 to 96.07 μM . Slightly higher antiproliferative activity of complex **C1** was observed in triple-negative breast adenocarcinoma cells MDA-MB-231, with IC_{50} 68.90 ± 1.73 μM and pancreatic adenocarcinoma cells PANC-1 with IC_{50} 69.84 ± 2.3 μM . Both cell lines are characterized by highly invasive and resistant phenotype. Human endothelial cells EA.hy 926 are easily accessible for therapeutics, and are considered as a good *in vitro* model for analysis of the pro/anti-angiogenic activity of drugs, thus were included in panel of cell lines for screening of drug action [33]. However, EA.hy 926 cells showed no significant sensitivity to rhenium complexes. Based on the IC_{50} values it was concluded that minor structural changes in the

picolinate part of ligand in complexes **C1–C3**, like the introduction of methyl groups, induced lost in the antiproliferative potential of rhenium complexes.

Table 1. Cytotoxic activity of the investigated rhenium complexes (**C1–C3**) vs. CDDP, in terms of IC₅₀ values ± SD, determined after 72 h treatment by MTT assay

Compound	Cell line / IC ₅₀ (μM)						
	A549	MDA-231	MCF-7	LS-174	PANC-1	Eahy.926	MRC-5
C1	96.07 ± 1.57	68.90 ± 1.73	86.43 ± 0.72	93.36 ± 3.73	69.84 ± 2.3	92.68 ± 3.94	80.22 ± 1.80
C2	>100	>100	>100	>100	>100	>100	>100
C3	>100	>100	>100	>100	/	>100	>100
CDDP	11.97 ± 1.04	7.3 ± 1.14	5.77 ± 0.55	22.22 ± 1.65	17.38 ± 3.42	12.13 ± 3.76	10.03 ± 0.27

Fig. 3. Cell survival diagrams for PANC-1 cells after 72 h of continual action of investigated compounds. Dose response curve of rhenium complex (black) or **CDDP** (blue). Data are representative for one out of three separate experiments with standard deviations.

4.2.2. Combinational study - Effects of VRP on rhenium(V) complexes treated PANC-1 cells

PANC-1 cells represent good model for *in vitro* screening of novel drugs and thorough understanding of the specific cellular and molecular mechanisms of tumor cell resistance. They are as well reported to exhibit reduced ability to accumulate drugs due to the expression of an ATP-dependent drug-efflux pumps with broad substrate specificity, often responsible for multidrug resistance (MDR) phenotype. Classical drug efflux pumps such as transmembrane glycoprotein Pgp or MRPs proteins have broad specificity for large

hydrophobic positively charged molecules [28,37,38]. In addition, results indicated higher sensitivity of human pancreatic adenocarcinoma cells, PANC-1, to action of **C1**, so those cells were selected for further mechanistic study. In the present study we investigated the effect of VRP on action of novel rhenium complexes with hydrophobic three-phenylphosphine (PPh₃) ligands, as VRP is a specific blocker of Pgp, and is also known to interact with calcium channels, potassium channels and adrenergic receptors [39,40]. VRP belongs to the first generation pharmacological inhibitors commonly documented to reverse multidrug resistance (MDR), and increase intracellular accumulation of anticancer drugs.

Antiproliferative effect of **C1–C3** was tested in PANC-1 cell, at three different concentrations (25, 50, 100 μ M) and in the presence or absence of VRP. Sensitivity of PANC-1 to VRP as a single agent, obtained by MTT assay for 72 h action is $IC_{50} = 139.44 \pm 1.92 \mu$ M. Therefore, sub-toxic concentrations below IC_{50} (30 or 100 μ M), were selected for combinational drug study. Results revealed that VRP differentially modulated cells sensitivity to tested rhenium complexes and **CDDP**, and are presented in Fig. 4. VRP caused dose dependent increase of antiproliferative potential of complex **C1** to IC_{50} (μ M) 51.38 ± 2.8 (Table S3.) Similar effect but to a lesser extent, was observed in combined action with less active complexes **C2** and **C3**. Results suggested that drug efflux transporters, which are generally known to facilitate export of an organic substrates, might have role in detoxification of tested rhenium complexes that carry hydrophobic PPh₃ ligands [41,42]. We have used **CDDP** as a standard, to compare the effect between these different metal complexes in pancreatic cancer cells. At the same treatment condition VRP seems to counteract the effect of **CDDP**. This result stands in line to the multiple evidences that tumor cell response to platinum based drugs is mediated *via* different mechanisms, and is less affected by drug-efflux Pgp transporters [43,44,45].

Fig. 4. Cell survival (% of control) of PANC-1 cells, following 72 h action of C1–C3 and CDDP in three different concentrations (25, 50, 100 μM), in the presence or absence of VRP (30 or 100 μM). Bar graphs show percentage of cell survival as average value ± SD of three independent experiments.

4.2.3. Combinational study - effects of L-BSO on PANC-1 cells treated with C1

Enhanced deactivation of cisplatin and other metal based drugs by thiol-containing molecules such as glutathione (GSH) is often demonstrated in tumor cells, and is another important mechanism of tumor resistance to anticancer agents [46,47,48].

Cole and coworkers pointed to the efflux of a range of GSH-conjugated molecules (GS-X) that occurs in tumor cells mediated by multidrug resistance-associated proteins MRPs [28,49,50]. Moreover, the cross resistance to different drugs in cisplatin resistant cell lines is actually conferred through this pathway. The concomitant increase in GSH expression is necessary for efflux of the detoxified drugs (GS-X), rather than the overexpression of the efflux transporter alone. Assuming that rhenium complex **C1** has similar routes of action/excretion as other metal based complexes, we investigated whether depletion of GSH, by specific inhibitor L-BSO, may affect sensitivity of PANC-1 cells to action of **C1**, as the most active one. L-BSO is a potent and irreversible inhibitor of γ - glutamylcysteine synthesis (γ -GCS), the rate-limiting enzyme for the biosynthesis of GSH [48].

Combination drug studies revealed that L-BSO at sub-toxic concentrations positively modulated cells sensitivity to **C1** and **CDDP**, results presented in Fig. 5. Enhancement of **CDDP** cytotoxicity in combination with L-BSO, is already documented [33,47] and was also observed in the present study. However, effect of L-BSO on action of **C1**, was rather pronounced at higher complex concentration (100 μ M), where cell survival decreased to 4.28 %. Depletion of GSH, enhanced activity of **C1** in PANC-1 cell, to IC_{50} values 57.67 ± 6.51 (μ M) (Table S3).

Fig. 5. Cell survival (% of control) of PANC-1 cells, following 72 h action of rhenium complex **C1** and **CDDP** in three different concentrations (25, 50, 100 μM), in the presence or absence of L-BSO (100 μM). Bar graphs show percentage of cell survival as average value \pm SD of at least two independent experiments.

4.2.4. Analysis of cell cycle perturbations

The effect of **C1** and **CDDP** on the cell cycle progression in PANC-1 cells, was examined in the presence or absence of sub-toxic concentrations of VRP. After treatment for 48 h, flow cytometry analysis was performed using PI staining, and results are presented in Figs. 6 and 7. Results showed that only **CDDP** caused changes of the cell cycle phase distribution, characterized by accumulation of cells in the S phase (29.96 % vs control 11.41 %) and G2 phase (41.46 % vs control 27.94 %). **C1** as single agent did not manage to induce changes in

cell cycle progression, while combined action with VRP (30 μM) caused slight arrest of cell cycle in the S phase. Sub-G1 fraction, characteristic for fragmented nuclei was in the level caused by VRP as single agent. At same treatment condition VRP seems to counteract the effect of **CDDP** action. These results are compatible with the results of combined drug study, and suggested the potential role of MDR/Pgp mediated drug export routes in cell response to the actions of rhenium complex **C1**.

Fig. 6. Effect of **C1** (100 μM) and **CDDP** (10 μM) on cell cycle phase distribution in PANC-1 cells, following 48 h continual action as a single agent or in combination with VRP (30 μM). Bar graphs show representative experiment of at least two independent experiments.

Fig. 7. Effect of **C1** (100 μM) and **CDDP** (10 μM) on cell cycle progression in PANC-1 cells following 48 h continual action as a single agent or in combination with **VRP** (30 μM). Cell cycle histograms were obtained by FACS flow and are representative of two independent experiments.

4.2.5. Morphological analysis of cell death

The morphological characteristics of PANC-1 cells following treatment by the **C1** and **CDDP**, were analyzed by fluorescent microscopy and acridine orange/ethidium bromide dual staining [33,36]. After 72 h of continual action of **C1** at concentration 100 μM , the majority of cells remained attached and retained cell to cell contacts, with the epithelial morphology like the untreated control cells. The fluorescent micrographs (Fig. 8.) showed appearance of

bright green dots located eccentrically or in the center of cells. Both chromatin condensation and nuclei fragmentation, are indicative for apoptosis. Occurrence of green fluorescence by intracellularly incorporated acridine orange is due to the preserved plasma membrane integrity. Treatment with higher concentrations of **C1** to approximate twice IC_{50} values (150 μ M), caused significant cell detachment, and cells started to shrink and round up. Orange to red colored chromatin was observed in the individual cells, which was characteristic for necrotic changes and secondary apoptosis.

CDDP, however caused both green (acridine orange) and orange (ethidium bromide) staining of condensed nuclei in the majority of cells, as well the occurrence of the enlarged intracellular compartments, which are indicative for compromised membrane integrity and simultaneous apoptotic and necrotic processes. After 72 h action of **CDDP**, at 10 μ M (below IC_{50} value), many of cells have already detached or lost cell to cell contacts. The observed differences in morphological characteristics and kinetics of cell death induction suggests that **C1** and **CDDP** exhibit different mechanism of action.

Fig. 8. Fluorescent micrographs present PANC-1 cells following 72 h continual treatment with **C1**, at concentrations 100 and 150 μM or **CDDP** (10 μM). Micrographs were obtained by the fluorescent microscope Axio Observer Z1, using AxioVision imaging software (Carl Zeiss MicroImaging GmbH). Acridine orange (green fluorescence) is a vital dye that stains both live and dead cells. Ethidium bromide (red fluorescence) enters only cells with disturbed cell membrane. Untreated cells were used as control and appeared almost uniformly green.

4. Conclusion

The research of metal chelating agents, coordination compounds and organometallic complexes is focused toward the modulation of the key aspects in the mechanism of drug action to overcome side effects, such as resistance and toxicity to healthy tissue [51,52,53]. Rhenium complexes merits particular attention, due to their wide range of oxidation states (-1

to +7), high affinity to N, S or O donor ligands and different coordination geometry, giving the opportunity to synthesize complexes with great structural diversity and different modalities of action. Within the present study we reported synthesis, structural characterization and *in vitro* antiproliferative potential of three rhenium(V) complexes of general formula $[\text{ReOCl}_2\text{L}(\text{PPh}_3)]$, with L = pyridine-2-carboxylic acid, 3-methyl-pyridine-2-carboxylic acid or 6-methyl-pyridine-2-carboxylic acid. Only **C1** showed dose-dependent cytotoxic potential toward triple-negative breast adenocarcinoma cells MDA-MB-231, with $\text{IC}_{50} 68.90 \pm 1.73 \mu\text{M}$ and pancreatic adenocarcinoma cells PANC-1 with $\text{IC}_{50} 69.84 \pm 2.3 \mu\text{M}$.

Drug combination study of **C1–C3** with VRP in PANC-1 cells, revealed that VRP as the specific inhibitor of efflux transporter Pgp, increased PANC-1 cell sensitivity to the action of **C1** in dose-dependent manner, and caused arrest of cell cycle in the S phase. Under the same treatment conditions, VRP counteracted the effect of **CDDP**. This result might not be surprising knowing that cellular transport and sensitivity to platinum agents is mediated via different pathways that manage copper homeostasis, and are less affected by drug efflux MDR (Pgp) transporters [44,45]. Depletion of GSH level by L-BSO in pancreatic adenocarcinoma cells, significantly potentiated action of **C1** and **CDDP**. The mechanism by which GSH diminish cisplatin cytotoxicity is well known [33,46,47,48,53], and include detoxification and facilitation of drug efflux. Present study indicated that GSH pathways may be as well involved in cell response to tested rhenium complexes that carry bulky PPh_3 ligand. Apparently, complex **C1** exhibits different kinetics and mechanism of cell death induction comparing to **CDDP**. Also, the mechanisms that attenuate cytotoxic activity of tested rhenium complexes do not affect **CDDP** at the same level. Further studies and additional structure-activity optimizations of rhenium complexes are important for gaining a

better insight in the mechanism of action in tumor cells, in order to develop new analogues with improved efficacy.

Declaration of Competing Interest

There are no conflicts of interest.

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Appendix A. Supplementary data

Supplementary data to this article can be found online at <https://>

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